

Participation of Girls in Law at University Level

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Abstract

This study focused on girl's participation in law at University level. The objectives of this study were to identify the participation of girls in law at University level especially in Madhesh University and find out the problems faced by girls while learning law. In dealing with such objectives, I used qualitative research design and Phenomenological approach to explore the multiple realities. To meet the objective, the researcher selected two law classroom and five legal girls who are studying in the sampled two law classroom. Classroom and girls were selected on the basis of non-purposive sampling. In this study, researcher used classroom observation form as a research tool. For this study, researcher observed fifteen days in deeply on sample classroom and sample girls. The data were analyzed with the help of descriptive and analytical method. The findings of this phenomenological study show that the participation of girls in law isn't similar to boys. Girls are near about boys on some approach that are leading the group, classroom submission, involving in extra-curricular activities. The participation of girls on classroom attendance and interaction with peers seen to be better than boys. It was also found that girls have many difficulties in learning law due to biological formation and function. Social rituals, early marriage is the main problems that faced by girls. It has also concluded that social belief system and teacher behavior towards girls would be positive to empower girls on University Education.

Keywords: girl, law, rituals, difficulties, empowered